

CITIZEN SOCIAL SCIENCE: TWO CASE STUDIES WITH DEAF AND HARD-OF-HEARING COMMUNITIES

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Abstract

Since issues of inclusion and accessibility become increasingly prominent within the community of citizen science scholars and practitioners, the need to gain a deeper understanding of conducting research in collaboration with underrepresented individuals also becomes increasingly relevant. Hence, by adopting a qualitative approach based on a case study analysis, the present paper draws on citizen social science projects with Deaf and Hard of Hearing (DHH) communities in Greece and Hungary. Specifically, it aims to highlight (1) the intervention designs and tools used, as well as (2) the challenges faced and the strategies deployed by DHH trainers. By adopting a cross-country, comparative approach, the authors aim to raise awareness and expand research towards inclusive and socially-oriented citizen science.

Keywords: citizen science; Deaf; Hard of Hearing; inclusion; underrepresented communities, case study.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the past two decades, public participation in scientific research, formally known as citizen science, has gained popularity among individuals and communities, with experts defining it as a way to “empower society [...] and support evidence-based policy” amid global challenges [1]. Nevertheless, the endeavour of democratising citizen science has mostly been developed in Western, Educated, Industrialised, Rich and Democratic (WEIRD) environments. Thus, the need to uptake and study citizen science projects with marginalised communities is becoming more prominent [2].

Besides Western socio-economic environments, for instance, in Central and Eastern European regions, citizen science has a relatively brief history. Rather, it has an “invisible” history in participatory research, masked by other locally-adopted terms and the dominance of positivist research traditions [3]. For example, in countries like Hungary and Greece, it is merely in the last decades that citizen science terminology has been strategically embraced, predominantly by natural scientists and action researchers [4]. In Greece, there is no national strategy or public body to connect citizen science initiatives that are currently segregated mostly around transnational cooperation projects with limited duration and resources.

As researchers increasingly acknowledge the value of inclusivity and accessibility in citizen science, we witness an increase in projects that are designed to facilitate and encourage the participation of individuals and communities that are underrepresented in science and society [5]. However, rising social inequalities in Western countries have further reinforced barriers to inclusivity and accessibility. Despite efforts to weaken the established scientific hierarchies, citizen science is an emerging field of research that has the potential to both reinforce and challenge the neoliberalisation of science. That is, on the one hand, the scarcity and lack of public funding available to researchers makes citizen science attractive as a low-cost means of obtaining data through public participation, testifying how neoliberal trajectories are produced in science [6]. And, on the other hand, involving marginalised and vulnerable communities in citizen science have the potential to strengthen social cooperation, cohesion and mutual learning. Collaborative citizen science might be able to counteract internal hierarchies within scientific endeavour, thus contributing to social transitions [7].

Regarding inclusivity, while not aiming to explore the notion of vulnerability in-depth in this paper, it is a core concept in our understanding of inclusive citizen science. Here, vulnerability is defined as the positionality of individuals and groups within society, and is characterised by a lack of adequate resources in terms of financial, social and political capital, access to knowledge, learning opportunities, health care, infrastructure and services. By addressing their special and context-dependent needs, an inclusive citizen science initiative has the potential to engage its participants and ameliorate the conditions that make individuals and groups vulnerable in contemporary societies [8].

Hence, inclusivity in citizen science renders that any member of society can participate in research, regardless of their vulnerability, social status, age, gender, religion, literacy level or sexual orientation [5]. In this context, it is the recognition of the positionality and vulnerability of the participants in a citizen science project that goes against pre-established social hierarchies in science-making [5] [9] and contributes to the democratisation of science. To counter-balance these hierarchies, constant co-learning and trustful, mutual exchanges between researchers, trainers, facilitators and participants can transform the basis of the citizen science endeavour.

1.1 Citizen social science

Although the terminology of citizen science has long been accepted and used, citizen social science (CSS) is a new conceptualisation that has gained attention in participatory research. While traditional citizen science involves public participation, it does not suffice to overturn the predominance of natural over social science research. Citizen social science, on the other hand, focuses on “the social issues, social phenomena and the social dimensions of the world” by encompassing participatory methodologies such as participatory action and co-created research processes. Further, the concept of “social” together with “citizen science” raises social issues that groups of citizens are interested in. Often, such social issues concern the participants’ livelihoods, conditions or experiences [10].

In this paper, we look into 2 case studies of CSS with DHH groups. Case study 1 takes place in Greece with DHH individuals engaging in plant biodiversity mapping and community wellbeing. Case study 2, from Hungary, involves a CSS project in which DHH individuals were involved throughout the research process, from setting the research agenda to the presentation of the research results.

1.2 Citizen Social Science with DHH groups

The present paper focuses on DHH groups in two countries from the periphery of Europe, namely Greece and Hungary. Although there are more than 750,000 Deaf people who use Sign Languages in the European Union [11], almost no attention has been given to their participation in citizen science so far (cf. section 2). Technology deployed to mediate scientific data collection and communication only partially offers a remedy to the exclusion of certain social groups from research processes that are otherwise open to public participation.

In this paper, we aim to analyse and discuss similarities and differences in the deployment of two DHH CSS initiatives, hereinafter Case 1 (Greek setting) and Case 2 (Hungarian setting). Both projects redirected the attention of the European citizen science community to DHH individuals and groups. The first citizen science initiative aimed to enhance their participation in citizen science initiatives. The second project, YouCount, focused on the evaluation of well-being and social inclusion among Hard-of-Hearing youth, exploring the challenges they face, such as employment and housing, while identifying the resources available to them. Drawing on empirical data and experiential knowledge generated in the two initiatives, this paper aims to share insights on (1) the intervention designs and tools used, and (2) the shared and differentiated challenges faced and strategies deployed by DHH trainers in each CSS action.

The paper is organised in four sections. The first section presents a literature review on citizen science with DHH people, followed by an introduction of the study's origin, scope and methodology. The second section introduces the two case studies while the third section discusses their main features in a comparative analysis paradigm. Finally, the fourth section provides recommendations for researchers and DHH trainers who wish to expand the field of activities further.

2 THE CURRENT LITERATURE REVIEW ON PARTICIPATORY RESEARCH WITH DHH PEOPLE

Conducting research with DHH individuals has gained significant attention during the last decade [12]; [13]; [14]. However, there is, still, considerable effort needed to ensure full and equal accessibility and participation of DHH communities in scientific research [15]. There are meaningful contributions that shed light on various aspects of DHH engagement in society, such as the role of technologies in enhancing DHH communication with hearing people [16]. However, there is a noticeable gap in citizen science-related literature. Hence, a first mapping of CSS projects for the DHH community was attempted by reaching out to the citizen science community via the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)'s mailing lists and Working Groups in the winter of 2023. Despite the effort, we were not able to identify any other DHH initiatives or projects at European level.

However, another type of research method and practice, namely Participatory Action Research (PAR) has a long history of engagement with DHH groups [17]. Owing to its co-creative and inclusive approach, PAR has been adopted by researchers in several contexts, including the identification of health inequities experienced by DHH communities [18] and the educational and learning outcomes of DHH students [19]. By bringing DHH individuals to the centre of the research process, PAR can empower DHH people who are seen as agents, rather than passive subjects of research.

In the field of citizen science, the limited number of projects with and for DHH people results in a lack of available knowledge to form a holistic understanding of how to build such a project or action. In the context of this paper, in Case 1, it became strikingly evident that only a few citizen science projects have been designed to encourage the participation of DHH people. Consequently, the team produced openly accessible materials such as the “DHH Guide in Citizen Science for Climate Change” and the online citizen science toolkit.

In Case 2, researchers [author], [author] and [author] (2023) published a paper that draws on their experiences of working with the DHH community. Their approach to citizen science with DHH individuals is from a “caring” research perspective that brings forward the need to forge deep and meaningful relationships with participants. Taking into account that building trust is a process and not a one-off event, YouCount’s researchers show a different way of doing research with DHH communities; one that is built on body awareness, safe space making and story sharing [20].

This paper further expands the insights and understanding acquired from the two case studies by integrating a cross-country dimension to enrich the dialogue and knowledge exchange between researchers who co-create CSS research with DHH people.

3 SCOPE OF THE RESEARCH

The goal of this paper is to convert the knowledge and experience of carrying out citizen science with DHH individuals into an insightful analysis and actionable recommendations serving as guidance to future researchers and DHH trainers in the field of CSS. The scope is thus twofold. First, it aims to serve as a cross-country analysis and qualitative understanding of the two CSS cases, in Greece and Hungary respectively. And second, it aims to propose a set of recommendations for scientists, trainers and individuals on the parameters that need to be considered when planning a citizen science project with DHH people.

4 THE ORIGIN OF THE PAPER

The beginning of this joint endeavour traces back to 2022, when researchers of Case 1, [author] and [author], connected with [author] (Case 2) during the activities of the European Citizen Science Association’s (ECSA) Empowerment Inclusiveness and Equity Working Group (EIE WG). At the 2022 ECSA EIE Working Group meeting, both case studies were presented, thus creating a direct link to each other. The connection was nurtured by a common motivation to share the insights and lessons learnt for the benefit of the DHH and CSS communities. Additionally, as citizen science is rather underexplored both in Greece and Hungary, our motivation to connect these two cases became part of our overall objective as a way to enrich the current national citizen science landscapes.

5 METHODOLOGY

Through co-working sessions, the two research teams framed the scope and methodology of the present paper, leading to the following research questions (RQs):

RQ1: What were the intervention designs and tools used in the two CSS projects?

RQ2: What were the shared and differentiated challenges faced by DHH trainers and the strategies they deployed to overcome those challenges?

For the case studies’ analysis, authors presented mainly qualitative and some quantitative data (e.g. number of participants) that were collected through co-creative templates containing the 6 features identified below. Influenced by the [2] study that showcases project coordinators’ experiences in citizen science, we bring researchers’ knowledge and experience from CSS projects with DHH people to retrieve useful recommendations.

Since our contribution is based on a comparative, case study analysis, we adopted a methodological approach, first proposed by [21]. Thus, we follow the case study approach which is particularly useful in “identifying major challenges for citizen science” [21]. The case studies’ descriptions is based on a predefined set of features, precisely: 1) scope, 2) methodology and citizen science level of engagement, 3) context (target groups; geography; workplan; tools), 4) challenges, 5) engagement strategies to overcome barriers, and 6) results. The identification of common features to guide the description of the two case studies allows for cohesion and cross-country reflections to be made by readers of the study.

Table 1. Key features of the 2 case studies.

Cases	Scope	Method & CitSci level of engagement	Context (target group, geography, workplan, tools)	Challenges	Engagement strategies to overcome barriers	Results
Case 1 [Greece]	Increase participation of DHH adults in CSS	Method: Collaborative research Level of engagement: collaboration	2 4-hour workshops in the city of Thessaloniki. Target groups: DHH students (12-15 y.o.), DHH adults Total: 20 participants Period: May- September 2023 Digital tool: iNaturalistGR app	Communication barriers. Relevance of citizen science topic. Different degrees of engagement of participants.	User-friendly educational materials (e.g. videos in Sign Language). Physical activity outside. Video testimonials. Advice from DHH trainers prior to the workshops. Meeting them in their space.	Data collected and stored in iNaturalist Increased awareness of citizen science. Feedback from DHH people and educators.
Case 2 [Hungary]	Social inclusion of DHH youth.	Method: Participatory Action Research (PAR) Level of engagement: Co-creation	Research group meeting: approx. 30, Living Labs - 5 events, 1 national workshop in Szeged with 40 people. Target group: DHH youth. Period: January 2021- August 2023. A research group of HH (5) and hearing (6) members. Digital tool: YouCount App	Communication barriers. Engaging Sign Language users (Deaf youths). Work-life balance for a prolonged research process.	Individual invitations and discussions prior to group meetings. Story sharing. Visual methods (cards). Co-creative processes (e.g. collaborative interviewing). Careful planning of interactions, spaces and agenda and constant feedback. Sign Language interpreter as gatekeeper of involvement. Building trust.	Qualitative data from interviews and focus groups on social inclusion. App data on city spaces. Information on inclusive spaces collected in an online database.

While the number of case studies of the present paper is limited, its main contribution consists of depicting the viewpoints of DHH trainers and researchers and their deep-rooted motivation for more research that amplifies DHH voices in citizen science.

6 THE CASE STUDIES

6.1 Case 1

Scope: The Greek CSS case study was carried out by [author] and [author] mainly in the framework of the Citizen Science For All project (CitSci4All). This 2-year Erasmus+ project (CitSci4All, 2022-2024, <https://citsci4all.eu/>) served DHH communities in Europe, aiming to increase the accessibility and inclusivity of citizen science. To achieve its goal, the project developed a series of DHH-oriented resources to facilitate the understanding and participation in citizen science. Empowered by the project

and moving beyond it, [author] and [author] continued working with the DHH community of Thessaloniki in a series of citizen science actions to enhance DHH citizen participation and engagement.

Description of activities: Within CitSci4All, [author] and [author] delivered two DHH oriented workshops in the city of Thessaloniki, Greece; a first one in May 2023 with 10 DHH Secondary School students and 1 DHH educator and a second in September 2023 with 8 DHH adults and 1 DHH trainer. The workshops were half-day physical events, where participants were introduced to the concept of citizen science and its contribution to the protection of biodiversity. In both workshops, [author] and [author] collaborated with DHH educators and trainers, who acted as Sign Language interpreters, and showed participants how to use the iNaturalistGR mobile application. After completing their mapping, DHH participants reflected on their experience in a group discussion and documented their reflections in a post-workshop questionnaire.

Citizen science methodology and type of participation: The citizen science workshops was co-designed with DHH experts (the DHH educator for the first activity, and the DHH trainer for the second). This allowed for the workshops to be structured according to the needs and special settings (e.g., mapping in a schoolyard, the city centre) of DHH individuals during that specific period (May and September 2023). Thus, at the beginning of each workshop, as a means to maximise accessibility for our target audiences, we made use of the CitSci4All Toolkit which contains educational material in the Greek Sign Language. Additionally, we made use of the iNaturalist app, which is a biodiversity mapping tool that empowers citizens to expand their own and collective awareness on biodiversity.

Engagement strategies: The engagement strategy was based on three features: a) the CitSci4All online Toolkit customised to the DHH needs, b) recommendations by the DHH educator and trainer, and c) the iNaturalistGR app. Specifically, we relied on the user-friendly educational materials (e.g., videos in sign language) of the toolkit to familiarise DHH people with citizen science concepts and methodology. Additionally, the presence of the DHH educator and trainer in both workshops was pivotal for our interaction with participants, creating a communication bridge and point of reference for all. The citizen science activity, carried out after each learning session, with the use of the iNaturalist mobile application, enhanced the motivation of DHH participants. Likewise, the video testimonials created with the DHH adults of the second workshop, acted as further motivation for the community to engage in citizen science and amplified their “voice”. Moreover, participants were involved in group discussions over their social inclusion in community well-being initiatives and reflected on the potential of CSS to empower them at individual and community levels.

Challenges and how they were addressed: A major barrier for the hearing to approach and engage with DHH participants was communication and achieving meaningful interaction throughout the workshops. To overcome this challenge, it was indispensable to seek the intervention of a DHH educator and a DHH trainer who acted as sign language interpreters and also as familiar persons that helped build trust between the researchers and DHH participants. Yet another challenge was delivering a citizen science workshop that caters for the needs of the target audiences, namely ensuring its relevance to their realities.

Considering the duration and communication limitations of each workshop, in collaboration with the DHH educator and trainer, we co-designed two citizen science activities that a) could be easily carried out by DHH people (cf. mapping plant biodiversity through the iNaturalistGR app), and b) addressed an urgent environmental issue in their area. Moreover, to address the different degrees of engagement by DHH participants, the workshops were planned to include a mix of learning and hands-on activities that maintained the interest of all participants throughout the activity.

Results: In terms of outputs, it is worth noting that this was the first attempt of our target audiences with iNaturalist and collecting and storing data (cf. images). Although only few of the participants were active in using iNaturalist (7 out of 20 participants used it systematically), we observed a series of results that may not be easily quantified or measured. For example, a) an increased awareness of biodiversity loss and the need to take action, and b) an interest to know more about citizen science and to be offered more opportunities to engage in it. Ultimately, the workshops were considered an opportunity for DHH educators and trainers to acquire knowledge and develop competencies in practising citizen science with their students and community members.

6.2 Case 2

Scope: YouCount (2021-2024, GA ID: 101005931), a youth citizen science project with hard of hearing (HH) youths for social inclusion, was launched in the city of Szeged, SE-Hungary, in collaboration between the Environmental Social Science Research Group and the Faculty of Economics Research Centre of the University of Szeged. The research involved in the project was a continuation of a previous university project that aimed to explore health equality issues of HH families in Szeged in 2018-2019

[22]. This recent study aimed 1) to investigate and articulate how HH youths evaluate their own subjective well-being and social inclusion, what challenges they perceive (e.g. employment, housing) and what resources are available to them and 2) to reflect on social inclusion and inclusiveness in the ongoing research process. The overarching goal of the research was to make the voice of HH youth heard, to provide space and platforms for them to express their needs and lived experiences and to disseminate these messages to the hearing communities in society.

Description of activities: The “Common Signs Research Groups” (CSRG), consisting of hearing, hard of hearing, senior, and junior members, was established in the autumn of 2021. THE CSRG organised approx. 30 regular research group meetings, conducted collaborative and participatory interviews and identified specific research questions for further focus on social inclusion of the HH youths in Szeged. The data collection through the YouCount Application was processed, recording experiences of social inclusion and accessible communication in the city. The data collection process is ongoing, aiming to build an online “Resource Database” of inclusive facilities in Szeged for the HH youths. The process and research outcomes were presented in Living Lab meetings and at a national workshop where urban actors and members of the HH and D/deaf communities were present in September 2023. Further steps include the dissemination of the results and the public launch of the Resource Database providing free access for the HH urban citizens.

Citizen science methodology and type of participation: In this youth, citizen social science project, a mixed methodology including participatory action and collaborative research was used. We conducted interviews using co-designed interview guides with open-ended questions, and organised storytelling discussion groups and focus groups. The resulting summarised field notes were analysed qualitatively. In identifying the research question and the data collection methodology, we followed a co-creative approach, making decisions together with the CSRG participants. However, for the YouCount application design, the type of participation was less co-creative. Rather it followed a regular consultative pattern, i.e. the developers regularly asked for feedback from the citizen scientists, but the initial platform was established by the developer.

Engagement strategies: During the recruitment process, invitations were sent out to possible HH young participants through informal and formal hubs and participants indicated their intention to participate in an online questionnaire. Following this phase, we organised individual face-to-face or online discussions with the respondents, where they were informed about the project and explored their motivations. The initial recruitment of interested students started in May 2021. Then, we started to work on the establishment of the Living Lab by meeting already known stakeholders and starting a collaborative stakeholder mapping exercise, following a snowball approach.

Summarising the process, recruiting HH citizen scientists was especially challenging. The interviews were first used as an engagement tool. Then, in recruiting for the app study, one senior academic and one Researcher Young Citizen Scientists (R-YCSs) who acted as “hub person” contacted approximately 30 HH (but not deaf) youths through emails and personal contacts. Finally, 4 of them agreed to join the app study, of which 2 remained in the study. The communication was conducted mostly via one-to-one meetings since invitations to group meetings were largely unsuccessful. It is important to highlight that, despite continuous efforts, no d/Deaf (sign language users) participated in the longer research process from the beginning, due to the difficulties of engagement.

Challenges and how they were addressed: Communication seems to be a crucial issue that has significant impact on the HH youth's overall well-being and also on our project. For example, HH youths can easily be excluded from group discussions, if more than one person talks or the interactions are very quick (or the background is noisy). Group settings are therefore especially challenging environments for the HH youths. Therefore, we realised from the beginning that the essence of the collaborative research process would be the development of communication skills and the organisation of space and time for clear interactions. Additionally, the overall perception of safety (in terms of emotional well-being, understanding, having enough time to communicate etc.) seemed a crucial factor for the participants and can pose further serious challenges. Therefore, establishing trust was an essential factor in this process and could not be accelerated or forced. Regarding the d/Deaf community, engaging into meaningful communication was an even more challenging process for the research group. The d/Deaf community may be considered as a separate, culturally diverse group in the HH community. Here, the sign language translator is an essential actor and an indispensable gatekeeper.

Results: The results/conclusions were drawn from three sources: 1) Qualitative interviews and focus groups with HH youths gave a perspective on the lived experience of HH youths in terms of inclusion; 2) the app study provided input for evaluating different facilities in the city that provide social inclusion; 3) the

data collection from the app study and individual questionnaires contributed to building of the Resource Database (spatially explicit map of inclusive spaces in the city). Summarising the outcomes, a few points can be highlighted: in our case, social inclusion can be summarised as “being able to participate in the life of the community through free and clear communication”. The most important, negative aspect of social inclusion is the experience of communication mismatch or error. Our research indicates that inclusion is a two-way process and requires commitment and actions from both sides, since the most important factor influencing inclusion was “other people’s behaviour”. Access to technology and the availability of different devices are key components in resolving communication mismatches.

7 DISCUSSION

The two CSS cases, situated outside the WEIRD contexts, bring insights into different levels of participation of the DHH community in scientific research. While the two cases’ research purposes, time frame, and level of participants’ involvement differ, they share the exploratory and co-learning manner in co-researching with DHH individuals. Both cases’ researchers and facilitators invited individuals from the DHH community to join their project as co-researchers and research contributors which was a novel endeavour. The joint work required both groups to expand their knowledge: facilitators began to learn how to communicate and set up research processes with DHH people, while citizen scientists began to conduct research both individually and in groups.

Despite the similarities of the groups in both cases, Case 1 focused mainly on a common, external research subject observed by the DHH citizen scientists (plant biodiversity), while Case 2 provided time and space for DHH participants to reflect on social inclusion and CSS research methods. In Case 1, a joint effort was deployed to encourage independent data collection via mobile apps to reinforce both the individual and the group-based scientific identity of DHH individuals. Empowerment in this case was driven by acquiring new scientific knowledge. In Case 2, HH citizen scientists became the research subjects themselves, reflecting on their emotions and social positionality. This case turned the researchers’ attention inward, toward their personal and lived experiences. This joint introspective observational process laid the foundations for trusting relationships in the HH research group.

Table 2. Similarities and differences of the two Cases.

Features	Similarities	Differences
Scope	Both cases were EU-funded and aimed to foster collaboration, participation and inclusion of DHH groups in scientific research.	The cases’ objectives were not similar; Case 1 aimed to enhance DHH participation in CSS, while Case 2 to foster DHH social inclusion. Case 2 lasted three years with several intervals and was part of a much bigger EU project (9 countries, with 9 parallel cases).
Method & CitSci level of engagement	Both Cases adopted collaborative research as the method to work together with DHH groups.	Case 1 opted for collaboration referring to the level of engagement, while it didn’t adopt a specific method for collaborative research. Case 2 adopted PAR as its key methodology and co-creation as its CS level of engagement.
Context (target group, geography, workplan)	Both cases engaged with DHH groups in an urban setting and used mobile apps for data collection purposes.	Case 1 was shorter (9 months) in terms of duration. Case 1 ran two face-to-face workshops (May-September), and a series of 4 more workshops at local level (city of Thessaloniki, Greece). Case 2 lasted for 3 years and organised a series of interventions at local and national levels. Case 2 involved HH participants (with hearing aids or cochlear implants) and no sign language users (d=Deaf)
Challenges	Both cases needed to address communication barriers and ensure the long-term engagement of DHH participants.	Case 1 faced the challenge of identifying a CitSci theme that would be relevant and appealing to its DHH group. Case 2 needed to address the power asymmetries and the work-life balance that its prolonged research process entailed (i.e. paid and voluntary researchers’ different availability)
Engagement strategies to overcome barriers	Both cases aimed to create an inclusive and safe environment for DHH participants. Organisers consulted with DHH educators before group meetings, while interactive and user-friendly materials and approaches were adopted.	Case 1 used the online toolkit and its DHH-friendly educational resources during its CitSci workshops. Advice by DHH educators and Sign Language interpreters was fundamental to connecting, engaging and building trust with the DHH group. Case 2 focused on individual invitations to participants, and developed a series of engaging processes, such as personal sharing and interviews.

Results	<p>In both Cases, quantitative data were collected and stored in online application databases.</p> <p>Qualitative data were also collected by surveys (Case 1) and interviews (Case 2).</p>	<p>Based on the feedback retrieved by DHH participants, Case 1 resulted in increased awareness and willingness among DHH individuals to participate in CS.</p> <p>Case 2 researchers gained a better understanding of what social inclusion is for DHH people in their newly formed research group, while particular information was collected on inclusive spaces in the city.</p>
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8 RECOMMENDATIONS

Our work on CSS with DHH individuals in two European countries emphasises the existing gap in designing accessible and inclusive citizen science projects at national and European levels. To contribute towards this direction, we share the following recommendations for implementing citizen science with DHH individuals. Our recommendations result from the hands-on experience acquired by authors while engaging with DHH people. Currently, it cannot be claimed that the proposed guidelines provide an all-encompassing scenario to carry out citizen science with this target audience. Nevertheless, the following recommendations may offer significant guidance to individuals attempting to organise work in this field:

- 1 Become familiar with the history and identity of your target groups as well as their special characteristics. The DHH community is heterogeneous, there is a distinct difference between the needs of d/Deaf (sign language users) and HH people in many respects.
- 2 Map and reach out to DHH-related institutions (e.g. educational institutions, associations, sign language centres) to establish contact with the community. Explore the “cultural brokers” - those who can act as bridges between you and the community in relational and practical terms. Engagement should be seen as a long-term trust-building process.
- 3 To ensure clear communication, the financial and infrastructural requirements of interpretation, written translation or any technological instrument should be considered during the planning phase. Time management should be also adapted to the needs of participants.
- 4 Build trust with your audience by being transparent and open. Be ready to ask and learn, acknowledging that one does not have to know everything a priori: Acquire regular feedback, needs assessments and critical reflections. Independent of the duration and the objectives of a project, intentions and goals should be clear to participants.
- 5 Ensure a safe space for engagement. It is essential to ensure the autonomy of the participants and enable everyone to participate and speak freely and equally in meetings. Constant reflection on the quality of communication and asking for feedback is a necessary step.
- 6 Opt for collaborative and co-creative citizen science projects that reflect the community’s needs. Being marginalised by scientists and researchers who treated them as objects of research rather than agents of change, it is advisable to design projects that are shaped collaboratively by DHH participants.
- 7 Be aware of potential, diverse health-related conditions of participants. DHH people may face several health issues that affect their degree of participation and ability to fully commit to the project.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Riemenschneider, D., Voigt-Heucke, S., The transformative potential of citizen science. European Research Council. Article accessed on May 7, 2024. Retrieved from <https://erc.europa.eu/news-events/magazine-article/transformative-potential-citizen-science>
- [2] Benyei, P. et al., Challenges, Strategies, and Impacts of Doing Citizen Science with Marginalised and Indigenous Communities: Reflections from Project Coordinators, *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 8 (1), 21, 2023. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.514>
- [3] Duží, B. et al., Exploring citizen science in post-socialist space: Uncovering its hidden character in the Czech Republic, *Moravian Geographical Report*, 27, 4, 2019. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.2478/mgr-2019-0019>
- [4] Czeglédi, A., Citizen science in the making: mapping participatory science projects in Hungary, *Proceeding of Science, Engaging Citizen Science Conference 2022 (CitSci2022)*. 2022.
- [5] Paleco C., et al., "Inclusiveness and Diversity in Citizen Science", in: *Vohland K. et al. (eds) The Science of Citizen Science*, pp 261–281, Springer, Cham. 2021. Retrieved from https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_14
- [6] Kimura, Aya H., and Abby Kinchy. "Citizen science: Probing the virtues and contexts of participatory research." *Engaging Science, Technology, and Society* 2 (2016): 331-361. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.17351/ests2016.99>
- [7] Vohland, K, et al., "Citizen Science and the Neoliberal Transformation of Science – an Ambivalent Relationship", *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 4, 1, p. 25, 2019. Retrieved from [doi:10.5334/cstp.186](https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.186).
- [8] Varga, D, et al., "How can Inclusive Citizen Science Transform the Sustainable Development Agenda? Recommendations for a Wider and More Meaningful Inclusion in the Design of Citizen Science Initiatives", *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 8, 1, p. 29, 2023. Retrieved from [doi:10.5334/cstp.572](https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.572).
- [9] Cooper, CB et al, Inclusion in citizen science: The conundrum of rebranding. *Science*, 372(6549), pp. 1386–1388, 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.abi6487>
- [10] Albert, A. et al., Citizen Social Science: New and Established Approaches to Participation in Social Research. In: *Vohland, K., et al. The Science of Citizen Science*, pp 119–138, Springer, Cham., 2021. Retrieved from https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_7
- [11] European Centre for Modern Languages, Facts about sign language. Article accessed on May 7, 2024, Retrieved from <https://edl.ecml.at/Facts/FAQsonsignlanguage/tabid/2741/language/en-GB/Default.aspx>
- [12] García-Terceño, EM., et al., The participation of deaf and hard of hearing children in non-formal science activities. *Front. Educ.* 8, 2023. Retrieved from <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/educ.2023.1084373/full>
- [13] Holmström, I, S Bagga-Gupta. "Patient or Citizen? Participation and Accessibility for Deaf and Hard-of-Hearing People in the Context of Interpretation in Sweden". *Scandinavian Journal of Disability Research*, 23, 1, pp. 209–223, 2021. doi:10.16993/sjdr.733.
- [14] Orfanidou, E., Woll, B., & Morgan, G., *Research methods in sign language studies: A practical guide*. John Wiley & Sons. 2014.
- [15] Nind, M., *Conducting qualitative research with people with learning, communication and other disabilities: Methodological challenges*. Project Report. National Centre for Research Methods. 2008.
- [16] Rodríguez-Correa, P. et al., Benefits and development of assistive technologies for Deaf people's communication: A systematic review, *Frontiers in Education*, 8, 2023. Retrieved from <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/educ.2023.1121597>

- [17] Beal-Alvarez, J., 'Action Research in Deaf Education: Collaborative, Representative, and Responsible Methods', In *Stephanie Cawthon, and Carrie Lou Garberoglio (eds), Research in Deaf Education: Contexts, Challenges, and Considerations, Perspectives on Deafness* (New York, 2017; online edn, Oxford Academic, 20 July 2017), Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780190455651.003.0012>
- [18] Barnett, Steven et al., "Community participatory research with deaf sign language users to identify health inequities", *American journal of public health*, 101,12, pp. 2235-8 2011. doi:10.2105/AJPH.2011.300247
- [19] Flores, Tanya L., "A Community-Based Participatory Research Project Involving Latino Families of Deaf and Hard-of-hearing Children.", *Journal of Community Engagement and Scholarship*, 12, 2, 2020. Retrieved from link.gale.com/apps/doc/A690099069/AONE?u=anon~369044c7&sid=googleScholar&xid=38020e2b
- [20] Mihók, B., Juhász, J., Gébert, J., Slow science and "caring" research – the transformative power of collaborative research with hard of hearing youths, *IJAR – International Journal of Action Research*, 19, 22, pp. 157-173, 2023. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3224/ijar.v19i2.06>
- [21] Butkevičienė, E. et al., Citizen Science Case Studies and Their Impacts on Social Innovation. In: *Vohland, K., et al. The Science of Citizen Science*. pp. 309-329, Springer, Cham. 2021. Retrieved from https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_16
- [22] Bajmócy Z., Mihók B., Gébert J., Furthering Social Justice for Disabled People. A Framework Based on Amartya Sen's Capability Approach. *Studia Universitatis Babeş-Bolyai Sociologia*, 67 1, pp. 69-84. 2022. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.2478/subbs-2022-0003>